

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New 4-Isogramines, 4-Arylthiomethyl and 4-Arylazo Derivatives of 5-Hydroxyindoles^ψ

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Mannich reaction of 5-hydroxyindoles (1-10) with formaldehyde and secondary amines produced the 4-isogramines (11-48). The nucleophilic displacement of dimethylamine from 4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles (11-15) was effected by heating them with thiophenols to get 4-arylthiomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles (49-58). The treatment of 5-hydroxyindoles (1-4 and 6-9) with aryldiazonium salt solution afforded exclusively 4-arylazo-5-hydroxyindoles (59-74). All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

4-Isogramines¹, sulphur containing indoles² and arylazoindoles³ are known to exhibit various biological activities. Hence it was thought of considerable interest to synthesise new 4-isogramines, 4-arylthiomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles and 4-arylazo-5-hydroxyindoles with a view to evaluate their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Results and Discussion

The required starting materials, viz. 5-hydroxyindoles (1-5) were prepared by the Nenitzescu reaction⁴. The bromination⁵ of the 5-hydroxyindoles (1-5) with bromine in acetic acid afforded 6-bromo-5-hydroxyindoles (6-10). These 5-hydroxyindoles (1-10) when subjected to Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and secondary amines, yielded the 4-isogramines of 5-hydroxyindoles (11-48) (Scheme 1).

1-Benzyl-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxyindole (12) showed the following spectral characteristics: ν_{\max} 1 683 (C=O) and 3 460 cm^{-1} (OH); δ 1.43 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, ester methyl), 2.38 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.57 (3H, s, C-2 CH_3), 4.16 (2H, s, C-4- $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, ester methylene), 5.26 (2H,

R = n-butyl, benzyl, phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *m*-chlorophenyl
X = dimethylamino, pyrrolidino, piperidino, morpholino

Scheme 1

s, N- $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.75 (d, J 9 Hz, C-6 H), 6.9-7.4 (6H, m, ArH) and 9.2 (1H, b, C-5 OH). These data confirmed the entry of aminomethyl function at C-4 of 5-hydroxyindoles (1-10).

Further, these 4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles (11-15) were heated with thiophenols to yield 4-arylthiomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles (49-58) with the evolution of dimethylamine (Scheme 2).

^ψPart of this work was presented at the 8th Annual Conference of the Indian Council of Chemists held at Tirupati, 1988.

R = n-butyl, benzyl, phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *m*-chlorophenyl
Y = H, Cl

Scheme 2

1-Benzyl-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-phenylthio-methyl-5-hydroxyindole (**50**) showed the following spectral characteristics : ν_{\max} 1666 (C=O) and 3378 cm^{-1} (OH); δ 1.37 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, ester methyl), 2.6 (2H, s, C-2 CH_3), 4.36 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, ester methylene), 4.9 (2H, s, C-4 $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.3 (2H, s, N- $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 5.6 (1H, s, OH), 6.75 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C-6 H) and 6.9–7.5 (1H, m, ArH).

Various 5-hydroxyindole-3-carboxylates (**1–4**) were treated with aryldiazonium chloride solution to yield exclusively 4-arylamino-5-hydroxyindole-3-carboxylates (**59–62**). The diazonium group entered only at C-4 position even though both C-4 and C-6 positions were vacant in these compounds (**1–4**). Similarly, 6-bromo-5-hydroxyindole-3-carboxylates (**6–9**) gave 6-bromo-4-arylamino-5-hydroxyindole-3-carboxylates in good yield (Scheme 3).

R = n-butyl, benzyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *m*-chlorophenyl
X = H, Br; Z = H, Cl

Scheme 3

1-n-Butyl-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-phenylazo-5-hydroxyindole (**59**) displayed the following spectral characteristics : ν_{\max} 1715 (ester C=O) and 3180 cm^{-1} (C-5-OH); δ 0.97 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, N $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.2 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, C-3

COOCH₂CH₃), 1.4–1.8 (4H, m, NCH₂CH₂CH₂CH₃), 2.62 (3H, s, C-2 CH_3), 4.1 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, NCH₂CH₂CH₂CH₃), 4.35 (2H, q, J 7.5 Hz, C-3 COOCH₂CH₃) and 7.3–7.9 (6H, m, ArH).

The doublet at δ 6.8 (J 9 Hz) due to C-6 H confirmed the entry of arylazo group at C-4 position of the precursor (**1**). The broad singlet due to C-5 OH observed at such a downfield (δ 14.25) suggests the existence of strong H-bonding between C-5 OH and 4-arylamino nitrogen. This peak disappeared on D₂O exchange.

The mass spectrum of the same sample (**59**) exhibited molecular ion peak M^+ at m/z 379 which is also a base peak. The fragmentation of M^+ produced fragments at m/z 333, 351, 302 and 274 by the loss of C₂H₆O, C₂H₄, C₆H₅ and C₆H₅N₂ respectively. The successive loss of CO and C₄H₈ from M^+ generated fragments at m/z 246 and 190 respectively. All these spectral data are in conformity with the structure (**59**) assigned.

Antimicrobial activity : All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *B. cirroflagellosus* using Norfloxacin as standard and for their antifungal activity against *C. albicans* and *A. niger* using Gressofulvin as standard by cup-plate method⁶. Test solution was prepared by dissolving the compound (1 mg) in dimethyl formamide (1 ml) and aliquat (0.1 ml) of this solution was used for evaluation of activity.

Of all the compounds (**11–74**) screened for antimicrobial activity, only few 4-isogramines exhibited activity comparable to that of the standards. The high zone of inhibition was observed for compounds **19** and **21** against *E. coli* and *C. albicans*, **14**, **19** and **21** against *B. cirroflagellosus* and **12**, **15**, **17**, **19**, **30** and **36** against *A. niger*. Rest of the compounds were found to be weak to moderately active. The halo-substituted compounds showed better activity than the others. These compounds were also found to be good antifungal agents rather than antibacterials.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 881 spectrometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃/TMS) on a GE spectrometer (300 MHz) and mass spectra on an Autospec EI spectrometer.

1-Substituted-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-dialkylaminomethyl-5-hydroxyindoles (11-48) : To a cooled mixture of the secondary amine (0.0025 mol) and formaldehyde (37%; 0.0025 mol) was added glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) dropwise by maintaining the temperature at 0-5°. A solution of 5-hydroxyindole derivative (1-10) in dioxan (5 ml) was added slowly to the above mixture followed by another lot of glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml). The reaction mixture was then heated to 90° on a water-bath for 10-15 minutes and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was poured into ice-cold water (50 ml) and suspended particles (if any) were removed by filtration. The filtrate was basified with ammonia (15%), and the separated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from suitable solvent (Table 1).

Table 1 (contd.)

22	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	191-92 ^b
23 (Methiodide)	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	128-30 ^a
24 (Oxalate)	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Morpholino	159-60 ^a
25	Benzyl	Morpholino	123-24 ^b
26 (Oxalate)	Phenyl	Morpholino	175-76 ^a
27	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	118-20 ^b
28 (Hydrochloride)	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	208-09 ^a
29	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Dimethyl-amino	102-03 ^c
30	Benzyl	Dimethyl-amino	120-21 ^c
31	Phenyl	Dimethyl-amino	148-49 ^b
32	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dimethyl-amino	162-63 ^b
33	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dimethyl-amino	123-24 ^b
34	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Pyrrolidino	110-11 ^b
35	Benzyl	Pyrrolidino	132-33 ^b
36	Phenyl	Pyrrolidino	140-41 ^b
37	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Pyrrolidino	180-81 ^b
38	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Pyrrolidino	175-76 ^b
39	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Piperidino	131-32 ^b
40	Benzyl	Piperidino	173-75 ^b
41	Phenyl	Piperidino	105-06 ^b
42	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	166-68 ^b
43	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	157-58 ^b
44	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Morpholino	118-19 ^b
45	Benzyl	Morpholino	141-42 ^b
46	Phenyl	Morpholino	139-40 ^b
47	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	171-72 ^d
48	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	180-81 ^b

* All Compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 42-73%.

** Crystallisation solvents : ^aethanol-ether, ^bbenzene-petroleum-ether, ^cethanol, ^dbenzene.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-ISOGRAMINES (11-48)*

Compd. no.	R	X	M.P.** °C
11 (Oxalate)	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Dimethyl-amino	169-70 ^a
12	Benzyl	Dimethyl-amino	105-6 ^b
13 (Methiodide)	Phenyl	Dimethyl-amino	> 300 ^a
14 (Methiodide)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dimethyl-amino	> 300 ^a
15 (Methiodide)	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dimethyl-amino	115-17 ^a
16	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Pyrrolidino	91-92 ^b
17	Benzyl	Pyrrolidino	99-100 ^b
18	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Pyrrolidino	128-29 ^b
19	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Pyrrolidino	99-100 ^b
20 (Methiodide)	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Piperidino	> 300 ^a
21 (Methiodide)	Benzyl	Piperidino	182-84 ^a

1-Substituted-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-arylthio-methyl-5-hydroxyindoles (49-58) : A mixture of 1-substituted-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxyindole (11-15; 0.001 mol) and thiophenol (0.0011 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 150-55° under nitrogen atmosphere till the evolution of dimethylamine ceased (0.5 h). The residue was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p.

40–60°) and then extracted with benzene. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave a solid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF
4-ARYLTHIOMETHYL-5-HYDROXYINDOLES (49–58)*

Compd. no.	R	Y	M.P. °C
49	n-Butyl	H	143–4
50	Benzyl	H	143–4
51	Phenyl	H	132–3
52	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	199–200
53	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	140–1
54	n-Butyl	Cl	140–1
55	Benzyl	Cl	154–5
56	Phenyl	Cl	192–3
57	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Cl	142–3
58	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Cl	197–8

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 44–55%.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF
4-ARYLAZO-5-HYDROXYINDOLES (59–74)*

Compd. no.	R	X	Z	M.P. °C
59	n-Butyl	H	H	121–23 ^a
60	Benzyl	H	H	107–08 ^a
61	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	H	145–46 ^a
62	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	H	128–29 ^a
63	n-Butyl	Br	H	185–86 ^a
64	Benzyl	Br	H	158–59 ^a
65	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Br	H	157–58 ^a
66	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Br	H	131–32 ^a
67	n-Butyl	H	Cl	150–52 ^a
68	Benzyl	H	Cl	184–85 ^b
69	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Cl	182–83 ^b
70	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Cl	148–49 ^c
71	n-Butyl	Br	Cl	151–52 ^c
72	Benzyl	Br	Cl	204–05 ^b
73	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Br	Cl	232–33 ^b
74	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Br	Cl	220–21 ^b

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 53–67%.

**Crystallisation solvents : ^aethanol, ^bbenzene, ^cbenzene-petroleum ether.

1-Substituted-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-arylaZO-5-hydroxyindoles (59–74) : Aryldiazonium salt solution prepared from suitable aniline (0.002 mol) in dilute HCl (50%; 15 ml) and sodium nitrite

(0.176 g, 0.0022 mol) in water (5 ml) was added to a vigorously stirred and cooled (10–15°) solution of 5-hydroxyindole derivatives (1–10; 0.002 mol) in NaOH solution (4*N*; 50 ml). The stirring was continued further for 1 h and the reaction mixture was acidified with concentrated HCl. The separated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from suitable solvent (Table 3).

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